

PHYSICAL EDUCATION FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN: DEVELOPING QUALITIES

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR UCHUN JISMONIY TARBIYA SIFATLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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Annotation: This article discusses the proper upbringing of the physical qualities of preschool children and the proper formation of their physical growth processes. There is also a discussion on what exercises to use for the proper growth and development of children in order to strengthen the child's body without overloading it.

Keywords: physical education, child's body, agility, strength, strength qualities, exercises, general physical exercises, explanation, physical upbringing.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning jismoniy sifatlarini to'g'ri tarbiyalash va ularning jismoniy o'sish jarayonlarini to'g'ri shakllantirish haqida so'z yuritiladi. Bola organizmini ortiqcha yuklamasdan mustahkamlash uchun bolalarning to'g'ri o'sishi va rivojlanishi uchun qanday mashqlardan foydalanish kerakligi haqida ham bahs-munozaralar mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy tarbiya, bola organizmi, chaqqonlik, kuch, kuch sifatleri, mashqlar, umumiy jismoniy mashqlar, tushuntirish, jismoniy tarbiya.

Introduction: We know that the great future of the state and the nation depends on the fact that young people in this state and nation grow up to be educated, educated and physically healthy. With this in mind, we need to give physical education to a child from an early age so that our young people today can be both mentally and physically healthy. We know that when a child exercises properly, his body hardens and growth is in the right direction.

In the process of exercising, children of this age develop the qualities of agility, speed, strength, endurance and flexibility. Given their anatomical and physiological characteristics, they have a greater chance of cultivating agility and speed than other qualities, and care must be taken to cultivate strength and endurance. However, the development of these qualities cannot be stopped at all, because the elements of strength and endurance are necessary for every movement,

and these qualities are manifested in other movements without the educator's will, such as walking, jumping, and throwing.

The flexibility of the nervous system of this age group provides a good opportunity for the equal development of physical qualities. This is because excitation and inhibition in the nervous system are related to the ability to exchange one with the other quickly. Especially during action games, you have to perform unplanned, extraordinary actions that are necessary for the game activity, and they manifest themselves in a short period of time, quickly replacing each other. This allows for easy development of agility quality. Nervous process accelerates the development of physical quality at a high speed. In a short period of time, running at a minimum speed, cycling and other exercises can contribute to the development of speed. In these exercises, it is important that the norms are chosen correctly and that they are interchangeable.

At this age, the neck, abdomen, back, and lumbar muscles are weak and do not develop well. Accordingly, the choice of exercises to develop the muscles of this group (walking, running, bending the body), to increase their walking speed, to show that they can achieve a higher performance than other qualities of movement, without which the child has difficulty performing daily physical exercises. would have encountered.

Before training preschoolers, they should be taught the importance of the exercise, its technique, the rules of a little movement, the rules of general and personal hygiene, and some elements of physical education. These young people are taught to exercise independently and in groups. Emphasis is placed on training in small groups, developing one's athleticism and interest in the results of older athletes, developing friendships, mutual support, attitudes toward toys, and morality. They should be organized in such a way that the physical qualities necessary for that age are combined with the education of mental, moral and aesthetic tastes. Aesthetics requires an understanding of the structure of the body, keeping the body upright, the smoothness and beauty of the movements, how to hold the head of the garment, and so on. During the physical education process, the main content of the educational process is the development of mental abilities, attention, comprehension, thinking, imagination, knowledge and other qualities in preschool children. Movement training begins at an early age. This is done on the basis of easy-to-difficult didactic principles, in a sequence, step by step, and teaches the basic knowledge of physical education, the requirements of personal, general hygiene rules.

Preschool physical education is based on general teaching methods and is based on the following principles of teaching: awareness and activity,

demonstration, strength and individuality, systematization, and student development .

When teaching a child to move:

a) The action to be performed in the demonstration method is demonstrated, imitated by the visual weapon, and the object is intended to be performed in the direction in which it is standing.

b) explains by word of mouth, using commands, narration, interrogation and other methods.

c) Exercise technique - used without changing or changing the conditions of the movement.

d) style of play and competition .

Demonstration methods are used in different age groups, depending on the age of the child and the degree of mobility.

The youngest children have limited motor skills and find it very difficult to imagine exercise. Demonstration techniques are often used to teach practice. In addition to demonstrating exercises, the use of visual aids, pictures, drawings, sketches, and models will make it easier to master exercise techniques during the exercise. Imitation exercises are very effective in teaching movement. Teaching the movement through the example of the movement of animals, birds and other animals stimulates children's interest in the image and activates the learning process.

The younger the children, the more interested they are in this technique. At this age, it is important to develop the ability to see and focus on objects. This, in turn, makes it easier to perform difficult exercises. For example, throwing over a high-hanging object, in which the body bends backwards, the weight of the body is placed on the back leg, or it jumps and hangs. Reaching the object, hanging toys and other objects is more effective. It is important to teach children to perform exercises without fear, and to develop movement skills, music is recommended for games with rhythm, tempo, singing, and singing.

Verbal method. Getting a child's idea of exercise helps them think and think. When both visual and verbal explanations are combined, children will be able to perform the exercises without difficulty as soon as they hear the name of the exercise or see and hear what is written. In clearer terms: we jump like a rabbit, like a crow .

The more experienced children are in motor skills, the easier it will be for them to use verbal explanations in their physical education. At the beginning of the lesson, the action is explained in detail, followed by an explanation and brief instructions. Instructions can be used to correct and warn of errors and evaluate

them. Commands and instructions are used to help preschoolers start, complete, rate, and rhythmize exercise. The simplest commands adopted in gymnastics, if the exercise begins to be performed without music, can be used mainly in older groups. The guidelines are mostly used in younger age groups. Many exercises, songs, and poems are performed in conjunction with reading a text about the events being told and how the action should be performed.

Asking children questions during the performance, teaching them to think, gives them a chance to learn more about the exercise and feel the movement. Interviews can also be a great way to gain an understanding of the exercise and the skills needed to perform the exercise, as well as reading books on physical education and sports, looking at pictures, and taking excursions to the stadiums.

The exercise methodology is very diverse. In pre-school children, the most common types of movement and exercise for all should be physical and physiological. At this age, it is necessary to choose more dynamic exercises, to use those that can have a physiological effect on many major muscle groups and the body at once, and to develop agility and motor coordination. Exercises from the elements of cycling, swimming, movement games, and sports meet these requirements.

Static exercise is not recommended for preschool children. These exercises replenish the nervous system and muscles, disrupt blood circulation and respiration, and strength exercises that require complete muscle contraction weaken the muscles and nerve joints. As you grow older, exercise changes and becomes more difficult. Exercises in kindergartens and preschools are included in the Preschool Physical Education Program (1994).

In children under one year of age, adults use passive movements, active movement elements include general exercises (with and without equipment, lying on your back, squats, turning your head in all directions), crawling, running exercises, climbing, and the simplest games. Massage is a key part of this age group program. The material on massage is given in the booklet "Sister vospitatelnitsa detskix yasley i mladshey grupp yasley sadov" (1963).

General exercises that are slightly more difficult for children from 1 to 3 years of age, physical and non-physical (ball, wood, gymnastic chair), basic movements (walking, running, balance exercises, deep jumping), the simplest exercises of purification (walking in a circle, one column, rowing), cycling, and swimming lessons. The program includes a wide range of movement games and dance exercises for this age group. The games obtained for this age group are characterized by the simplicity of the rules, the ease of determining the winner, and are mainly played in the form of various images, in the form of imitations (birds, animals, etc.).

It is taught to children from 3 to 7 years of age, and in practice it is called the "frontal" method of organizing children's activities. For example, more attention is paid to certain elements of the exercise to be performed. When showing long throws, attention is paid first to the initial position and then to the remaining elements. Therefore, the return must be repeated in different variants. Repetition of the exercise is carried out only after the practitioner has a thorough understanding of the material techniques being mastered. Strengthening of motor skills is carried out in different conditions - in the form of games, competitions, performance of various tasks. "Who can do this exercise well," "Who can run fast to the flag and come back," "Who can shoot the ball farther," or "Who can hit the target." The uniqueness of physical education is reflected in the interaction of teaching methods.

In the teaching of preschool children, imitation is used to imitate what you see, vice versa, down, up, back, and so on. Introducing play techniques that increase the emotionality of teaching.

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